

CONTENT AND TASKS OF MOTHER TONGUE TEACHING IN GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract: This article describes the aims and objectives of the mother tongue teaching methodology course, teaching literacy, reading in and out of class, grammar, phonetics, spelling, word formation, and methods of developing students' speech. At the same time, methods of applying scientific and theoretical information into practice are disclosed.

Key words: society, stage, vocabulary, aesthetic and labor, phonetic and graphic, spelling and punctuation.

The content of teaching the mother tongue in schools is adapted to the task of our state for the school at the current stage of society's development. These tasks are multifaceted, and their fulfillment is aimed at developing the minds of students, giving them ideological-political, moral, aesthetic and labor education. As a result of teaching the mother tongue, the students will be able to express their thoughts grammatically correct, stylistically clear, meaningful, following the tone and write it correctly. This task is a unique feature of the Uzbek language as a subject of study, and it is carried out in connection with general educational tasks aimed at forming the student as a person.

The content of the knowledge provided in the native language course is about the sound structure of the Uzbek language and the methods of expressing sounds in written speech (phonetic and graphic); about the change of words and the connection of words in a sentence (grammatical, that is, morphological and syntactic); about the morphemic composition of the word and the methods of word formation (about word formation); about the lexical-semantic group of words (lexicological); constitutes knowledge of correct writing principles of the Uzbek language and the use of punctuation marks (orthographic and punctuation). This knowledge is manifested, firstly, in grammatical, phonetic, word formation concepts, and secondly, in graphic, orthographic, and punctuational rules. In addition, the Uzbek language course includes phonetic, graphic, morphological, syntactic and other skills and competencies. In the process of learning a language, students are also trained to develop skills (interdisciplinary skills) that are common to many other educational subjects. In pedagogy, such interdisciplinary skills include analysis, synthesis, abstraction (visualization of language phenomena), generalization, grouping, comparison, etc. This purposeful work on the formation of students' skills provides an opportunity to activate their educational activities and acquire knowledge successfully. Special skills formed from the mother tongue course and interdisciplinary skills are formed in the educational process without separating from each other.

The knowledge to be imparted and the special skills to be developed in students are recorded in school programs and state education standards.

For learning in primary grades, knowledge was chosen that would be the basis for conscious mastery of the language and the formation of graphic and spelling skills in students. In the field of phonetics and graphics, students acquire knowledge that allows them to correctly

understand the sound composition of a word, the specific characteristics of vowels and consonants, the importance of sound in a word in differentiating its meaning, as well as the ability to consciously determine the ratio (connection) between the sound and graphic form of a word, the ability to write a word correctly. is created. From the field of morphology, knowledge of great practical importance was selected for the conscious mastering of the word and its correct use. Primary school students learn word groups (noun, adjective, number, pronoun, verb) at different levels starting from the 1st grade.

The "Vocabulary" section is not provided separately in the program, but students get information about lexical-semantic groups of words (synonyms, antonyms), their lexical meanings in the process of studying word groups and word structure.

Language phenomena are studied in terms of their meaning (semantics), construction, and function.

Since the day of independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan has put the policy of reforming the society on the agenda. As in all sectors, the policy of reforming the education sector has been consistently implemented.

In the "Introduction" section of the state education standard, "Primary education is aimed at forming the child's ability to think logically, intellectual development, worldview, communicative literacy and self-awareness, to be physically healthy, to feel the beauty of material existence, to enjoy beauty and elegance, it is emphasized that it is necessary to inculcate and respect national customs and to follow them.

As stated in the state education standard, in the "requirements imposed by the state and society at the stage of primary education", compatibility, proportionality, and harmony in the fields of education should be fully ensured. In this regard, setting the standard of primary education allows to modernize the content of the educational process and the content of the components of the same content, to use new, modern pedagogical technology in the process of primary education.

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